

SIGNIFICANCE OF INSTRUCTING PERUSING AND TUNING IN ABILITIES IN ENGLISH LESSONS

Nizomova Nargiza Aliyevna

Fergana State University

Foreign languages Faculty

Assistant of the Department English practical course

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12593041>

Abstract: In this article talks about almost significance of educating perusing and tuning in abilities in English lessons, as well as, the positive impacts to understudy who talk more than one dialect have progressed memory, problem-solving and critical-thinking ability, upgraded concentration, capacity to multitask and superior tuning in and perusing abilities.

Keywords: Reading and listening skills, English lessons, writing, student, teaching, memory, time management.

Introduction

English is one of the broadly utilized dialects within the world. So, you need to be a familiar English speaker and to know the world as much as you'll be able. To form objectives in your desire for learning English you ought to take a few counsel:

There are four abilities in learning English which are perusing, tuning in, talking, and composing.

And which of them is the primary? The foremost imperative thing you must bear in intellect is that perusing and tuning in are inputs though talking and composing are yields. In other words, in the event that you want to make strides your talking and composing aptitudes you ought to to begin with ace the aptitudes of perusing and tuning in. There are a few ways that you just. can do so, which I will attempt to summarize.

1) Perusing

Perusing is an important way of picking up data in dialect learning and it is fundamental aptitudes for a dialect learner. There a part of perusing works out. But all these readings must be exhausted constrained time. You ought to perused express by express. Examined as much as you'll . But your perusing must be dynamic. It implies merely must think almost the structure, new words and others as you perused. There is no require that you simply adhere to a few complicated linguistic use structures or try to understand all the new words you come over, but the fact that you just see them for the primary time and recognize them at whatever point you see them for example in other expressions or books

is sufficient. It would be better to prepare yourself a note pad so you can type in down the imperative words or structures in it. This can be the exceptionally valuable strategies of learning dialect. To start perusing, I suggest the simple reading books step by step. They classified by level of trouble.

2) Listening

As for tuning in, there are two choices:

- Aside from perusing, you'll tune in each day for about 30 minutes.
- You'll be able only concentrate on your reading and ended up apt at your reading, at that point you'll capture up on your tuning in.

Tuning in, one of the implies of dialect communication is utilized most broadly in people's every day lives. In expansion, a parcel of tuning in exercises may be a great way of broadening your lexicon. On the other hand, it moreover makes a difference you to make strides your tuning in comprehension. When you are skillful and native-like at perusing, your tuning in expertise develops naturally. Since you have got lots of inputs in your intellect, you can easily guess what the speaker is going to say. This never implies that you simply should not hone tuning in. Practice is important. Only through the hone you'll be able improve your tuning in. For tuning in, I suggest cartoons, moves, songs and radio program. Once more, the thing to remember is being dynamic in tuning in and ideally taking a few notes.

In case you take after these pieces of advice, along with your perusing and tuning in aptitudes your talking and composing will be improved automatically, and you'll be able be beyond any doubt that with a small exertion they will ended up culminate.

References:

1. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DIDACTIC SYSTEM IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN NON-PHYLOLOGICAL DIRECTION Makhsetova Zuhra Turebaevna Almalyk Branch of Tashkent State Technical University Named After Islam Karimov, English Language Teacher EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH Volume 1 Issue 9, December 2021
2. PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN TRANSLATION Makhsetova Z.T. Master's Student Chirchik Pedagogical Institute Tashkent Region "Экономика И Социум" №7(74) 2020
3. Dushatova, S., & qizi Norinboyeva, D. J. (2022). CHET TILIDA NUTQNI TINGLAB TUSHUNISH VA UNDA FRAZEOLOGIZMLARNING O'RNI. YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS, 1(7), 66-71.

4. Shokhsanam, D., & Makhmudova, M. (2022). BENEFITS OF DAILY READING. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE, 1(8), 28-32.
5. Dushatova, S., & Burgutova, G. (2022). CHET TILLARINI BILISHNING FOYDALARI. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE, 1(8), 40-45.
6. qizi Dushatova, S. B., & qizi Qodiraliyeva, N. I. (2022). EFFECTIVE METHODS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4, 1(5), 63-67.
7. ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES VOLUME 1 | ISSUE 3 | 2020 Zuxra Makhsetova ACADEMIC SUBJECT INTEGRATION IN TEACHING PEDAGOGY IN DIFFERENT ESTABLISHMENT